

Spectroscopic ellipsometry study of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ bulk poly-crystals

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Abstract

The present study addresses to the synthesis and determination of the dielectric function of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solutions with $x = 0.4$ and 0.8 over the range $1 - 4.5$ eV by spectroscopic ellipsometry analysis, with the aim to achieve a suitable band gap tuning. The dielectric function of the samples is determined using the Adachi model. From the analysis the lowest E_0 transition and high energy E_{1A} and E_{1B} transitions are identified. It is found that the band gap varies nonlinearly on composition in the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ alloys and band gap values as large as 1.87 eV are obtained. These results are essential for the design of efficient tailored photovoltaic solar cells and show the high potential of the kesterite compounds for the development of low-cost sustainable future solar cells.

Keywords: $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ alloys, ellipsometry, polycrystals, kesterites, optical spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy.

1. Introduction

The $\text{Cu}_2\text{-B}^{\text{II}}\text{-C}^{\text{IV}}\text{-X}_4$ ($\text{B}^{\text{II}}=\text{Zn}$; $\text{C}^{\text{IV}}=\text{Ge, Si, Sn}$; $\text{X}=\text{S, Se}$) quaternary chalcogenide semiconductors have become attractive for thin film solar cells as absorbers [1,2] because of the low-cost, nontoxic and abundance of their constituent elements in the earth's crust. On the efficiency side, however, they have

not yet treated as viable competitors for Si, CdTe or Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ photovoltaic materials, which is due to the high concentration of deep intrinsic defects, leading in particular to a low minority carrier lifetime, electrostatic potential fluctuations and band tail states [3-5]. Recently, the band-gap engineering has been explored by alloying Cu₂ZnSnSe₄ or Cu₂ZnGeSe₄ with S [6-10] or Sn [11-19], respectively. This has led to improved electronic properties of the absorber layer and an increase in conversion efficiency of the Cu₂ZnSn_xGe_{1-x}S(Se)₄ solar cells up to 13 % [12,13, 20-22, 23]. Although Si is much more abundant in the earth's crust than other elements, there are not many studies on an alternative alloying Cu₂ZnGeSe₄ with Si. The possibility of band gap adjustment from ~ 1.4 eV for Cu₂ZnGeSe₄ [24, 25] to ~ 2.4 eV for Cu₂ZnSiSe₄ [25, 26] has been demonstrated. Note that an alloying Cu₂ZnSn(S,Se)₄ with Si is proved to be ineffective [27-29] due to a considerable mismatch between Sn and Si [30] which leads to a high formation energy. However, the case of a substituting Ge with Si in Cu₂ZnGeSe₄ compound seems to be more promising as the difference in the cation radius is smaller.

In this context in Ref. [31] the synthesis and structural properties of Cu₂Zn(Ge_xSi_{1-x})Se₄ with ($0 \leq x \leq 0.37$ and $0.58 \leq x \leq 1$) mixed crystals have been studied. It was found that Cu₂Zn(Ge_xSi_{1-x})Se₄ with $0 \leq x \leq 0.37$ crystallized in the wurtz-stannite type structure (space group Pmn2₁) [31,32]. However, the Ge-rich side of the solid solution adopted the stannite (space group I $\bar{4}2m$) or the kesterite (space group I $\bar{4}$) type structure. Besides, it was found by density functional theory calculations that the Cu₂ZnSi_{0.25}Ge_{0.75}Se₄ alloy has an optimal band gap of 1.45 eV and a better structural stability due to less deep-level defects negligible lattice distortion (0.28%) and negative formation enthalpy (-0.34 meV/atom) [33].

Apart from this earlier work [31] there have been no other experimental results in the literature to clarify the particularities of the Cu₂Zn(Ge_xSi_{1-x})Se₄ solid solutions. In this paper we address the synthesis and the dielectric function of Cu₂Zn(Ge_xSi_{1-x})Se₄ solid solutions with $x = 0.4$ and 0.8 through spectroscopic ellipsometry analysis.

2. *Experimental details*

Cu₂Zn(Ge_xSi_{1-x})Se₄ solid solutions with the initial load $x = 0.4$ and 0.8 were grown by modified Bridgman method through the direct interaction of high purity elements: Cu (5N), Zn (5N), Ge (5N), Si (6N) and Se (5N). Synthesis was carried out in an evacuated and sealed quartz ampoule covered inside with graphite. A vertical furnace with temperature gradient of 15 °C/cm along the furnace axis was used for processes. The synthesis procedure included heating to 1100 °C, holding at this temperature for 10-

12 hours and subsequent slow (10 °C/h) cooling. The prepared ingots were exposed to long-term (2 months) annealing at 600 °C for homogenization. The ingots were then cut into disc that were treated following the polishing method of Albornoz et al. [34] to achieve a clean and suitable optical surface for which the effects of roughness and of the residual oxides at the samples' surface are minimized.

The sample's chemical composition was determined by energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis (Oxford Instruments, model INCA Xsight) attached to Hitachi S-3000 N scanning electron microscope. Raman scattering spectra were measured using the Horiba Jobin-Yvon FHR 640 monochromator coupled with CCD detector. The spectra were measured in backscattering configuration though the special probe designed in IREC. Solid state (532 nm) and He-Cd gas (442 nm) laser were used as excitation source.

Optical spectra were recorded with a variable-angle spectroscopic ellipsometer (J.A. Woollam VASE) at room temperature in the photon energy range of 1.0 – 4.5 eV at an incidence angle of 70°.

3. Theoretical background

The complex dielectric function $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_1 + i\varepsilon_2$ of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solutions is modelled by the dielectric function (MDF) of Adachi [35,36], which enables an adequate description of the ε -function over the measured photon energy range for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ and $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSiSe}_4$ semiconductor materials [25]. In brief, the contribution of the interband transitions to the dielectric function has two components, one from the band gap transition, E_0 and the other from the high-energy $E_{1\beta}$ ($\beta = A, B$) transitions:

$$\varepsilon(E) = \varepsilon^{(0)}(E) + \varepsilon^{(1)}(E), \quad (1)$$

where E is the photon energy.

The following $\varepsilon^{(0)}(E)$ and $\varepsilon^{(1)}(E)$ terms are defined:

$$\varepsilon^{(0)}(E) = AE_0^{-3/2} \chi_0^{-2} (2 - (1 + \chi_0)^{1/2} - (1 - \chi_0)^{1/2}) \quad (2a)$$

$$\varepsilon^{(1)}(E) = B_{1A} [1 - (E/E_{1A})^2 - i(E/E_{1A})\Gamma_{1A}]^{-1} - B_{1B} \chi_{1B}^{-2} \ln(1 - \chi_{1B}^2), \quad (2b)$$

where $\chi_0 = (E + i\Gamma_0)/E_0$ and $\chi_{1\beta} = (E + i\Gamma_{1\beta})/E_{1\beta}$, and A and Γ_0 are the strength and the broadening energy of the E_0 transition, respectively, and, $B_{1\beta}$ ($\beta = A, B$), $\Gamma_{1\beta}$ ($\beta = A, B$) and $E_{1\beta}$ ($\beta = A, B$) are the strength, the broadening and energy of the corresponding high-energy transitions. Here, the E_{1A} (E_{1B}) is the energy transition for the 2D-M₁ (2D-M₀) critical points (CP's), respectively. It should be noted that we also considered a Gaussian type broadening mechanism for the high energy interband transitions by modifying the broadening parameters in Eq. (2b) as follows [37]

$$\Gamma_i'(E) = \Gamma_i \exp\left(-s_i \left(\frac{E-E_i}{\Gamma_i}\right)^2\right) \quad (3)$$

where s_i is a non-dimensional parameter, Γ_i is the broadening parameter, E_i is the transition energy, and i is 1A or 1B. On the other hand, for the lowest E_0 transition we found that this modification is not justified as the calculated s - parameter approaches zero value.

The ellipsometry parameters Δ and Ψ are calculated using a three-phase model [38] which takes into account presence of rough surface layer in the bulk material of the polycrystalline sample. In particular, the dielectric function of the surface layer is calculated with the Bruggeman effective medium approximation (EMA) [39] under the assumption that this layer containing 50 % of air voids and 50 % of bulk sample. To evaluate MDF parameters we employ the simulated annealing (SA) algorithm [40] and find the global minima of the following objective function [41]:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\left| \frac{\Delta(E_i)}{\Delta_{\text{exp}}(E_i)} - 1 \right| + \left| \frac{\Psi(E_i)}{\Psi_{\text{exp}}(E_i)} - 1 \right| \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where Δ_{exp} , Ψ_{exp} , and Δ , Ψ are the experimental and calculated values of the ellipsometry parameters at the E_i point, respectively, and N is the number of the experimental points.

4. Results and discussions

Chemical composition measurements were performed in different areas of the samples disks that allowed to determine the regions with compositions closer to the nominal stoichiometry. Subsequently the measurements were performed in different points of the selected region yielding the average composition of the samples (see Table 1) that was used for further analysis.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the investigated $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ samples.

Sample	Cu at. %	Zn at. %	Ge at. %	Si at. %	Se at. %	Cu/(Zn+Ge+Si)	Zn/(Ge+Si)	Ge/(Ge+Si)
Ge04	27.6	10.3	5.9	8.5	47.8	1.1	0.7	0.4
Ge08	30.3	6.7	11.6	4.0	47.4	1.4	0.4	0.7

Raman scattering spectra were measured under two excitation wavelength, 442 and 532 nm. Due to resonance effect the first one is sensitive to the possible presence of ZnSe and GeSe₂ secondary phases [42], while due to the absorption the second one allows to define the presence of CuSe phase [43] and other polymorphs of Ge-Se system [42]. Peaks of none of these secondary phases were observed in the analyzed samples in selected regions of the disks. Moreover, the general shape of the Raman spectra [44] of the analyzed samples allows to conclude that quaternary phase is the main one for both solid solutions with no or residual amount of secondary phases. The small blue shift of the peaks with increase

of the Si content correlates well with the position of Raman peaks of the end members of the series, $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ [45] and $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSiSe}_4$ [46]. However, absence of a reference spectra of this solid solution does not allow to estimate the exact values of Ge/(Ge+Si) ratio.

Fig.1. Raman scattering spectra of the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solutions measured under 532 nm (main panel) and 442 nm (inset) excitation wavelengths. Here in the main panel the numbers indicate the position of Raman peaks of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solutions, while the vertical lines in the inset indicate the position of first and second order Raman peaks of ZnSe secondary phase, expected in the analyzed samples.

Figure 2 shows the experimental (points) and the calculated (solid lines) spectra for samples Ge04 and Ge08. Overall, the features observed in Δ and Ψ spectra are well reproduced by the MDF model, except some deviations in the region below the fundamental absorption onset. These deviations from the model can be explained by the presence of absorption tails [47] and to the presence of minor surface layer non idealities (i.e. roughness /oxidation). Table 2 shows the calculated MDF parameters and the values of the relative errors. The thickness of the rough surface layer is determined in the range 5-7 nm, which is acceptable result taking into account the surface preparation method for the SE measurements. The high frequency dielectric constant, ϵ_∞ , is directly related to the MDF parameters and is expressed as $\epsilon_\infty \approx A/(4 * E_0^{1.5}) + B_{IA} + B_{IB}$. The extracted values of ϵ_∞ equal to 7.81 and 8.63 for the Ge04 and Ge08 samples, respectively. The ϵ_∞ becomes higher with increase of Ge composition which is consistent with results on the end points of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solution [25].

The determined values of the lowest transition E_0 , which corresponds to the band gap transition, are 1.56 and 1.87 eV for Ge04 ($x=0.41$) and Ge08 ($x=0.78$) samples. Based on our results and those reported for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ ($x=1.0$, $E_0 \sim 1.4$ eV) and $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSiSe}_4$ ($x=0$, $E_0 \sim 2.3-2.4$ eV) [18, 25], it reveals that band gap varies nonlinearly with composition for the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ alloys. It has been recently calculated that the bowing parameter, that describes nonlinear dependency of the band gap dependence, is 0.56 for the kesterite $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solution [48]. This relatively high value of bowing

coefficient could explain the observed band gap dependency. However, it should be remarked that samples with low Ge content ($x < 0.37$) do not adopt a kesterite type structure, but instead they crystalize in the wurtz-stannite type structure [31]. At present the required correction of those theoretical predictions of the band gap dependency due to the different crystal structure is unclear. On the other hand, we do not have enough band gap data points to experimentally quantify the band gap dependence on composition.

Above the fundamental gap the E_{1A} and E_{1B} high-energy transitions are calculated at 2.60 and 4.18 eV for Ge08 sample and at 5.32 and 3.68 eV for Ge04 one (Table 2). A direct comparison between these two sets of data is rather difficult as we found a different order in energy for these transitions: $E_{1A} < E_{1B}$ for Ge04 sample and $E_{1A} > E_{1B}$ for Ge08. Nevertheless, this result is consistent with the order of high-energy transitions in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ and $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSiSe}_4$ [48] and is most likely related to the crystal structure transformation from kesterite to the wurtz-stannite type for $x < 0.37$ in $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solution [31]. It is also should be added that the highest energy transitions (4.18 eV for Ge08 sample and 5.32 eV for Ge04) are determined with less accuracy because they occur near or beyond the experimental spectral range.

Since the knowledge of the optical properties of the absorber material is necessary for the application, design, and optimization of the actual photovoltaic cells we additionally have evaluated the optical constants such as the refractive index and the extinction coefficient (Fig. 3(b)), as well as the normal incidence reflectivity and the absorption coefficient (Figs. 3(c) and 3(d)).

Fig. 2. Experimental Ψ and Δ spectra (points) and numerically calculated (solid lines) using three phase model (air, surface and bulk layers) for samples Ge04 and Ge08 of the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$.

Table 2. Model parameter values.

Parameters	$A(eV^{1.5})$	$E_0(eV)$	$\Gamma_0(eV)$	B_{1A}	$E_{1A}(eV)$	$\Gamma_{1A}(eV)$	s_{1A}	B_{1B}	$E_{1B}(eV)$	$\Gamma_{1B}(eV)$	s_{1B}	Error	
Samples												$\Psi\%$	$\Delta\%$
Ge04	4.9	1.56	0.02	0.5	2.60	0.27	0.1	7.5	4.18	0.7	0.1	4.0	1.3
Ge08	8.3	1.87	0.04	2.1	5.32	0.54	0.4	4.9	3.68	0.4	0.1	2.4	1.5

Fig. 3. Numerically calculated (a) dielectric function $\epsilon(E) = \epsilon_1(E) + i\epsilon_2(E)$, (b) extinction coefficient, k , and refractive index, n , (c) normal-incidence reflectivity, R , and (d) absorption coefficient, α , by using the MDF model and the SA algorithm for the samples Ge04 and Ge08 of the $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ polycrystals

5. Conclusions

The $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})\text{Se}_4$ solid solutions with the band gap variation from ~ 1.4 eV for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ to ~ 2.4 eV for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSiSe}_4$ belong to a number of a very promising absorber compound as top cell in tandem devices. In this work we have determined the room temperature dielectric function for compositions with $x = 0.4$ and 0.8 by spectroscopic ellipsometry in the $1.0\text{--}4.5$ eV photon energy range for polycrystalline samples grown by the modified Bridgman method. Their high quality was confirmed by Raman scattering measurements obtained at different excitation wavelengths, which show no peaks of the secondary phases in the analyzed samples.

The Adachi model was used to analyze the obtained spectroscopic ellipsometry data and permitted to clearly identify the lowest E_0 transition as well as high energy E_{1A} and E_{1B} transitions and their variation with composition. The optical constants such as the refractive index and extinction coefficient and the normal incidence reflectivity and absorption coefficient were evaluated. The reported data are essential for the design, and optimization of the future low-cost sustainable kesterite based photovoltaic cells with tunable and wide bandgap.

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